

A Museum of Biology in the capital of Brazil

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MO1) Mobilizing specimens for factbased conservation in the face of a global biodiversity crisis, Lecture Theatre 2, Appleton Tower, 11 Crichton Street, EH8 9LE, June 7, 2022, 11:30 AM - 1:00 PM

Brasília is the capital of Brazil, located in the middle of the neotropical savanna called Cerrado. There are constant threats to this biome caused by the expansion of cities and agricultural development. For the last 60 years, researchers from the University of Brasília have been studying, describing, and collecting the Cerrado's fauna. Thus, ten zoological collections and an herbarium were assembled and comprehend several of the largest collections of Cerrado species. However, the research in the university often remains in the academic realm, not reaching the population. An efficient way to make the academic knowledge accessible is through scientific dissemination, in natural history museums. Regardless, Brasília is one of the few important capitals in the world that does not present a natural history museum. Furthermore, curators suffer with similar problems among themselves, and have scarce university support. Therefore, creating a Biology Museum, in the Institute of Biological Sciences at University of Brasília, will promote temporary and permanent exhibitions that may bring awareness of scientific discoveries to the general population and connect the people to the university. Also, the Museu will stimulate the scientific production and strengthen the collections. Exhibitions inclusive to people with several disabilities are one of our main goals, with objects that stimulate tactful, visual and auditory interaction. The museum can also present a positive impact on conservation, since people familiarized with the nature that surrounds them tend to cause less human impact because of the interest generated by this engagement. Therefore, this museum intends to be a place of coexistence, with direct contact with nature and the research on this nature, being a site for scientific dissemination. Also, virtual visits are planned to add accessibility for people worldwide.

